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Abstract

This document contains the script and visual material accompanying the core part of the deliverable, a demo video showing the key functionalities of Beacon applied to the cancer field with examples adapted to colon cancer use cases. We have developed a custom UI and adapted the backend accordingly to fulfil the needs of the cancer research community. We have envisioned clinical or translational researchers as the end users of this implementation. Here, we describe and show the potential of Beacon not only as a cancer data discovery tool but also as a mediator for semantic and syntactic harmonisation.

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Statement of originality

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the current bottlenecks in cancer research is the availability of large volumes of patient related data. In that context, data discoverability appears as the first barrier to access relevant health data. Beacon v2 promises to facilitate the findability of genomic and associated clinical data without breaching a patient's privacy.

With this implementation we have tailored Beacon v2 and its user interface to the needs of EOSC4Cancer use cases, focused on colorectal malignancies. In this demonstrator we describe the key functionalities of Beacon and show how it can be applied to the specific needs of the cancer research field, using precise examples relevant to colon cancer research. We underscore the potential of the query expansion to semantically harmonise clinical terms in the background and the inherent capability of the Beacon model to be used as a proxy for structural harmonisation of different data models. With additional examples we also demonstrate the cross-query function that facilitates the combination of genomic and clinical information. Here we provide the script and figures presented in the accompanying [video](#), which is the core of this deliverable/demonstrator.

EOSC4cancer Beacon: <https://cancer-beacon-demo.ega-archive.org/>

Video Demo: <https://youtu.be/8A1vLvTqsk>

DEMONSTRATOR SCRIPT

Slide 1 - Title page

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Federated discovery of genomic and clinical data using Beacon

Deliverable 2.4

Teresa García-Lezana
Jordi Rambla

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Federated discoverability for assembling virtual cancer cohorts. With this demonstrator we aim to show the potential of Beacon for assembling cancer cohorts to enhance their discoverability.

Slide 2 - Index

Index

1. What is Beacon?
2. Demonstration genomic queries
3. Beacon network
4. Query expansion - as proxy for semantic interoperability
5. Demonstration of query expansion
6. Beacon Model - as proxy for syntactic interoperability
7. Demonstration cross-queries
8. Reference Implementation

First, we will introduce Beacon and demonstrate how to perform genomic queries using the [user interface](#). We will also present the Beacon network and how it works. Next, we will focus on the potential of Beacon to facilitate data interoperability by showing the query expansion, for semantic interoperability, and presenting the Beacon model, for structural interoperability. Finally, we will show a demonstration of how to perform complex cross-queries, or in other words, queries that combine genomic and clinical information.

Slide 3 - Beacon overview

Overview

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What is Beacon?

Beacon is a genomics discovery tool which allows to aggregate worldwide genomics dataset through a shared query protocol.

HOW BEACON SEARCH WORKS?

Step 1: go to Beacon and sign in

Step 2: write a query
How many female patients with colon cancer and over 70 years

Step 3: get your results from the search:

- Boolean (yes/no)
- Count
- Case data

340 PATIENTS FOUND

Let's try it!

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In short, Beacon can be defined as a genomic discovery tool that allows the aggregation of worldwide genomics datasets through a shared query protocol. It works in a simple manner: users write the genomic or clinical information of their interest and then, the Beacon engine looks within the datasets and returns the requested information in an aggregate manner. Let's try it to explore its full potential.

EOSC4cancer Beacon: <https://cancer-beacon-demo.ega-archive.org/>

Slide 4 - Genomic queries

DEMONSTRATOR 1 - Genomic queries

DEMONSTRATOR - Colorectal cancer cohort - PanCancer Atlas

Query 1: One mutation – Response: **count**

Number of patients with the mutation KRAS-G12C

Query 2: multiple mutations – Response: **boolean**

Patients with mutations in KRAS and in TP53

The dataset used in this demonstrator is the colorectal cohort from the PanCancer project, publicly available in cBioportal. It contains genomic data, just somatic mutations of well-known oncologic effects, and associated clinical data.

For the first demo we will start trying two different genomic queries, one for a single mutation and another including an additive combination of genes.

- For the first case, let's imagine a clinician trying to recruit colon cancer patients having the mutation KRAS-G12C for a clinical trial to investigate a new small molecule targeting specifically that mutation. Let's imagine that she (or he) wants the response as counts.
- For the second case, we can imagine a translational researcher who has generated double knock-out mice for KRAS and TP53 and wants to know if there are patients with the same tumour profile. Maybe later they will request the full data and analyse the genetic profile in humans. Let's imagine that the researcher just needs the response as boolean.

Demo 1

See video min 1:18

The screenshot shows the search interface with the following elements:

- Header: Home icon, BEACON INFO, LOG IN.
- Search bar: "How many?..." (highlighted), Individuals dropdown, "having ..." label, search input containing "geneId:KRAS&aminoacidChange:p.Gly12Cys", Clear button, and search icon.
- Filters:
 - Diseases: Colon adenocarcinoma, Mucinous Adenocarcinoma of the Colon and Rectum, Rectal Adenocarcinoma.
 - Demographics: Age at diagnosis (with filter icon), Female, Male.
 - Treatment: Radiation Therapy, Chemotherapy, Fluorouracil, Oxaliplatin, Zoledronic Acid, Irinotecan.
 - Histopathology: Ascending colon, Caecum, Descending colon, Tumor stage I, Transverse colon, Tumor stage II, Hepatic flexure, Tumor stage III, Splenic flexure, Tumor stage IV, Sigmoid colon.
 - Others: Button with group icon.
- Variant section: "Mutations in: gene: KRAS aminoacid p.Gly12Cys" (highlighted), "Mutations in: gene KRAS", "Mutations in: gene TP53".
- Footer: Home icon, BEACON INFO, LOG IN.

The screenshot shows the search interface with the following elements:

- Header: Home icon, BEACON INFO, LOG IN.
- Search bar: "Do you have?..." (highlighted), Individuals dropdown, "having ..." label, search input containing "geneId:KRAS&aminoacidChange:p.Gly12Cys,geneId:KRAS,molecularAttributes.geneIds=TP53", Clear button, and search icon.
- Filters:
 - Diseases: Colon adenocarcinoma, Mucinous Adenocarcinoma of the Colon and Rectum, Rectal Adenocarcinoma.
 - Demographics: Age at diagnosis (with filter icon), Female, Male.
 - Treatment: Radiation Therapy, Chemotherapy, Fluorouracil, Oxaliplatin, Zoledronic Acid, Irinotecan.
 - Histopathology: Ascending colon, Caecum, Descending colon, Tumor stage I, Transverse colon, Tumor stage II, Hepatic flexure, Tumor stage III, Splenic flexure, Tumor stage IV, Sigmoid colon.
 - Others: Button with group icon.
- Variant section: "Mutations in: gene: KRAS aminoacid p.Gly12Cys", "Mutations in: gene KRAS" (highlighted), "Mutations in: gene TP53" (highlighted).
- Footer: Home icon, BEACON INFO, LOG IN.

Slide 5 - What is Beacon?

What is Beacon?

1. Beacon is a data discovery tool that facilitates findability of human data worldwide while **safeguarding patients' privacy**.
2. The Beacon Project is a **global standard** developed by the **Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)** Initiative
3. Follows a **federated model**, which means that health organizations always keep their data on site.
4. The Beacon instances can have **different levels of data access**: open, registered and controlled.
5. The Beacon **response can be provided with different levels of granularity**, from aggregated (boolean or counts) to detailed (case data).
6. Focused on the findability of **genomic and clinical data** in healthcare and research
7. Being expanded to complementary data sources for example cancer registries or images

Now that we understand the potential of Beacon, let's see the key points of what Beacon is in detail:

- As we have previously mentioned, [Beacon is a data discovery tool](#) that facilitates the findability of human data worldwide while safeguarding patients' privacy.
- The Beacon Project is a global standard developed by the [Global Alliance for Genomics and Health \(GA4GH\) Initiative](#).
- It follows a federated model, which means that health organizations always keep their data on site.
- The Beacon instances can have different levels of data access: open, registered and controlled.
- And, as we have already seen, the Beacon responses can be provided with different levels of granularity, from aggregated (Boolean or counts) to detailed (case data).
- Beacon is focused on the findability of genomic and clinical data in healthcare and research. Currently, it is being expanded to complementary data sources such as cancer registries or cancer imaging.

Slide 6 - Beacon Network

Beacon Network

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Beyond individual Beacons, they can be connected creating what is known as a Beacon network. In other words, individual Beacons installed at different institutions can be connected creating a network and this network allows the communication of multi-institutional beacon projects through a unique interface, enhancing the discoverability power of beacon.

Slide 7 - Beacon Network. How does it work?

Beacon Network

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So, as we have seen, Beacon networks are collections of multiple Beacon instances, probably from different institutions. From a more technical point of view, the Beacon networks rely on a central service managing the integration of nodes and having a unified access interface. But, how does it work for the end user? The process is the same as using an individual Beacon. The user sends a query, which is distributed to the different nodes by the Beacon engine. The different responses are then aggregated and displayed as a single unified response to the user.

Slide 8 - Query expansion overview

Query expansion - Harmonization at concept level

Ontology tree for colorectal cancer (MONDO)

HORIZONTAL EXPANSION

NCIT: C2955

SCTID: 1286877004

MONDO:0005575

COLORECTAL CANCER is a type of cancer that affects the colon (large intestine) or rectum.

VERTICAL EXPANSION

NCIT:C4349

NCIT:C7966

NCIT:C9383

Colon adenocarcinoma, mucinous carcinoma of colon and rectal adenocarcinoma are subtypes of colorectal cancer

The Beacon query expansion is a functionality aimed at reconciling the diversity in health data representation, facilitating interoperability by automatically harmonizing data at a semantic level.

To further understand the query expansion, it is key to keep in mind that human health datasets are extremely diverse. As a result, different datasets often use different ontologies to represent the same or similar concepts. Beacon must span this diversity of data representations to achieve the ultimate goal of connecting health research data.

Let's clarify what is an ontology. An ontology is a system to represent a set of concepts and the relationship between them. They should be universally interpreted, both human and machine-readable. Here we have a snapshot of an ontology, MONDO, showing the family tree for colorectal cancer.

To exemplify the potential of the query expansion we need to keep in mind, as we said before, that health data containing equivalent information can be represented in many different ways. Or in other words, different datasets use different ontologies to represent the same concept. Example 1) The concept of colorectal cancer can be represented with different codes by the different ontologies (NCIT, SNOMED or MONDO), or 2) different subtypes of colorectal cancer (such as colon adenocarcinoma, mucinous carcinoma or rectal adenocarcinoma) can be grouped by the same parental term (colorectal cancer).

Slide 9 - Query expansion: vertical and horizontal overview

Query expansion

Harmonization at concept (semantic) level

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More in detail, the so-called query expansion includes two dimensions: vertical expansion and horizontal expansion.

The horizontal expansion is meant to harmonise equivalent concepts represented by different ontologies, while the vertical expansion is meant to harmonise concepts hierarchically, from parental to childhood terms. In this example, both malignant neoplasm of colon, and malignant neoplasm of breast belong to the parental term malignant neoplastic disease in SNOMED and can be classified as such.

Slide 10 - Query expansion: Beacon Network

Query expansion

Semantic harmonization of Beacon network

How does the query expansion work within a Beacon network? When a user queries data using a specific term, the beacon network and the query expansion perform this vertical and horizontal ontology screening and gather all the related terms. In this example, using “malignant neoplasm” as the selected term, the network would be able to identify horizontal synonym terms represented by different ontologies - malignant neoplastic disease in SNOMED and malignant neoplasm in NCIT - as well as identify vertical relationships, identifying colon cancer as a childhood term of cancer. The Beacon Network will return all relevant responses to the user.

Slide 11 - Beacon framework and model

Beacon design

Framework: describes the overall structure of the API requests, responses, parameters, the common components, etc.

Model: describes the domain entities and the relationships between them

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Beacon v2 is organised in two main blocks: the [Beacon Framework](#) and the [Beacon Model](#). The Framework includes the features related to Beacon instances, and describes the structure of the API and common components, while the Beacon Models describes the domain entities and the relationships between them. To obtain interoperability between Beacon instances, Beacon v2 includes a recommended model for clinical genomic diagnosis and research. However, separating the Framework from the Model allows other disciplines to adopt the Beacon concept without departing from the standard itself and keeping the possibility of applying a model that is relevant to the domain. For example, Beacon for images or Beacon for cancer registries.

Slide 12 - Beacon model

Beacon model - Harmonization at structure level

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The beacon model, as shown in the figure, implements default entities such as individual, biosample, observed genome variation or variant information and their logical relations, as well as other additional technical concepts. Local researchers are responsible for structuring the data so it can be queried by Beacon.

Slide 13 - Beacon model: Syntactic interoperability

Beacon model

Harmonization at structure (syntactic) level

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How does the beacon model relate to other clinical data models? The Beacon architecture supports the discovery across other data standards, such as openEHR, related to the storage of clinical data, FHIR for clinical data exchange, or OMOP CDM for the storage of clinical data for secondary use. Or even with other research platforms such as cBioPortal, which has no pre-established model. The “Individuals” domain within the Beacon model can be tailored and mapped to the components of these standards.

As an example, in this figure we can see how some simple attributes such as “patient diagnosis” and “diagnosis date” are structured in different ways in the represented models. Here, Beacon can serve as a proxy for structural harmonization and interoperability.

Slide 14 - Cross Queries

DEMONSTRATOR- genomic and clinical data

Other more complex queries than can be performed:

Patients with colon cancer at advanced stage treated with oxaliplatin that present mutations in TP53

- Query in patients
- Response: counts

What is the mutational status of APC of colon cancer patients(>65) with lesions located in descending colon?

- Query in variants
- Response: Full response

Now, we will demonstrate the full functionality of Beacon v2 with queries integrating genomics and clinical information.

For the first example, we are interested in knowing the number of colon cancer patients at an advanced stage (Stage IV), treated with oxaliplatin and mutations in TP53.

For the second example, we are interested in knowing the mutational status of APC (query in variants) of colon cancer patients, older than 65 years with lesions located in descending colon.

Demo 2

See video min 10:26

How many?... Individuals having ... histopathology=Stage IV,treatment=Oxaliplatin,molecularAttributes.geneIds=TP53

Diseases

- Colon adenocarcinoma
- Mucinous Adenocarcinoma of the Colon and Rectum
- Rectal Adenocarcinoma

Demographics

- Age at diagnosis
- Female
- Male

Treatment

- Radiation Therapy
- Chemotherapy
- Fluorouracil
- Oxaliplatin
- Zoledronic Acid
- Irinotecan

Histopathology

- Ascending colon
- Caecum
- Descending colon
- Tumor stage I
- Transverse colon
- Tumor stage II
- Hepatic flexure
- Tumor stage III
- Splenic flexure
- Tumor stage IV
- Sigmoid colon

Variant

- Mutations in: gene: KRAS aminoacid: p.Gly12Cys
- Mutations in: gene: KRAS
- Mutations in: gene: TP53

eoesc cancer v0.5.3

Can you give me details on?... Genomic variants having ... histopathology=Descending colon,diseases.ageOfOnset.iso8601duration>65,geneId:APC

ID age at diagnosis > Value 65

Diseases

- Colon adenocarcinoma
- Mucinous Adenocarcinoma of the Colon and Rectum
- Rectal Adenocarcinoma

Demographics

- Age at diagnosis
- Female
- Male

Treatment

- Radiation Therapy
- Chemotherapy
- Fluorouracil
- Oxaliplatin
- Zoledronic Acid
- Irinotecan

Histopathology

- Ascending colon
- Caecum
- Descending colon
- Tumor stage I
- Transverse colon
- Tumor stage II
- Hepatic flexure
- Tumor stage III
- Splenic flexure
- Tumor stage IV
- Sigmoid colon

Variant

- Mutations in: gene: KRAS aminoacid: p.Gly12Cys
- Mutations in: gene: APC

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Slide 15 - Beacon v2 reference implementation

The Beacon v2 Reference Implementation

- The functionalities of the Beacon API go beyond the presented UI demo. The API is framed within the GA4GH standard and can be used for other cancer types and diseases.
- To simplify the process of lighting a Beacon, a free and open-source 'reference implementation' of the latest specification has been developed.
- The **Beacon v2 Reference Implementation (B2RI)** is an "out-of-the-box" Beacon instance developed with ELIXIR, which **facilitates Beacon deployment**.

The functionalities of the Beacon API go beyond the presented UI demo. The API is framed within the GA4GH standard and can be used for other cancer types and diseases.

More information about Beacon can be found in [this webpage](#).